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Love and Sacrifice: Her Timeless Legacy

'Twas a Sunday noon, our minds at ease,
Sharing hot meals, baraku aroma curling the air.
Children roaming, screaming, laughing free.
No luxuries to flaunt, just memories spoken aloud.

Sitting on the porch, coffee in our hands.
Stories rise as white strands are gently plucked.
Wrinkles may show, but her beauty shines through.
Etched in faith, each bearing quiet strength.

She raised me, now she's raising mine.
That foundation built on love, sacrifice, and wisdom.
With a melting heart, I gaze upward, awash in gratitude.
Sigh... I pray my daughter feels this, one day as a mother.
Thank you...mom!